

**Project Deliverable D-JRP17-
WP7.Del3 – Final draft of data
management plan**
Workpackage 7

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: INIAV, APHA, BfR, FLI,
IZSAM, NDRVMI, INSA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-JRP17-WP7.Del3 - Final draft of data management plan
Project Acronym	IDEMBRU
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

FINAL DRAFT OF DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Objective

The aim was to finalize the organization of the Data Management Plan, evolve it according to the latest updates of the LSAM website and present it to the consortium for final validation.

Result

DMPs are sorted per work package and type of documents created. First DMP for each work package includes the standard operating procedures. Second DMP is dedicated for the raw data inventories and files. Third and following DMPs are specific for each work package regarding the results, protocols, and various parts that will become integrative part of the toolkit.